

METHODOLOGY FOR TRAINING FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN DESIGNING EDUCATIONAL CONTENT

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Abstract: This article analyzes the methodology for teaching future primary school teachers to design educational content. The importance of designing educational content for all parties involved in the teaching and learning process, including teachers, is highlighted. The article reflects on the importance of designing educational content to improve the quality of the education system, as well as to make the educational process innovative and effective. The relevance of modern lesson design in primary education and the importance of designing educational processes in primary schools are discussed.

Keywords: educational content, design, primary education, modern lesson, innovative technology, pedagogical process, project-based education.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЮ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО КОНТЕНТА

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется методология обучения будущих учителей начальной школы проектированию образовательного контента. Подчеркивается важность проектирования образовательного контента для всех сторон, вовлеченных в процесс обучения и преподавания, включая учителей. В статье размышляется о важности проектирования образовательного контента для повышения качества системы образования, а также для того, чтобы сделать образовательный процесс инновационным и эффективным. Обсуждается актуальность современного проектирования уроков в начальном образовании и важность проектирования образовательных процессов в начальной школе.

Ключевые слова: образовательный контент, проектирование, начальное образование, современный урок, инновационные технологии, педагогический процесс, проектное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

In our changing world, the education system, like other areas, is developing rapidly. This shows that new concepts are emerging in the education system. In our country and abroad, prestigious universities and research institutes are primarily focusing on primary education and conducting research on the formation of the intellectual abilities of future primary education teachers, the consistent development of their creativity and creative abilities, and the formation of a well-educated, morally upright person. If we consider primary education as an example of a building, the builder who laid the foundation of this building is the primary school teacher. Significant reforms are being implemented in our country to create a system of training primary school teachers that meets international standards. This situation solves the problem of training high-quality, competitive teachers for all educational areas in high demand in the field of education, including primary school. As a result of the reforms carried out in recent years and in line with the principle of “Creating access to quality education throughout life” in the international education concept set for 2030, it is required to develop the design of educational content for future primary education teachers in higher education, to create new ideas that differ from the traditional approach, to develop the ability to think outside the box, to be individual, and to take initiative.

Designing educational content is the process of creating an educational program to provide students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies.

MAIN PART

Project-based education has been used in pedagogy for more than 300 years. According to the research of the German pedagogue M. Knoll, the emergence of the concept of "project" dates back to the 16th century and is associated with the attempts of Italian architects to turn their activities into a profession, declaring architecture a science and elevating it to the level of academic disciplines. As a result of the emergence of the engineering profession at the end of the 18th century, the educational project began to be used first in France, then in Germany, Austria, Switzerland, and in the middle of the 19th century in technical and industrial higher schools in the USA. According to sources, the project method appeared in the USA in the second half of the 19th century, and its founder is the American educator and psychologist John Dewey. The design of the educational process is viewed as a value-oriented, deeply motivated, highly organized, purposeful professional activity aimed at changing the pedagogical reality. The term "project" has passed into the field of social sciences from the technical sphere, and means "the main idea of rebuilding the state of a particular area in accordance with specific rules." [2,17]

Design in the educational process is a specially organized purposeful educational activity by the teacher that ensures the student's independent action, from searching for a problem, planning and organizing activities to solving it, to mass evaluation. Design is an event, a process that occurs in a certain sequence over a certain period of time, leading to a unique result. It is appropriate to distinguish between the broad and narrow meanings of the term design. In the current conditions, there is no area of activity in society that does not work on the basis of design. In particular, the use of design methods in the educational process, instilling design skills in the growing younger generation, is difficult, but design is a process that directly affects the interests of the country and society. It requires will, consistency, great mobilization, dedication, and most importantly, serious aspiration and motivation from both educational subjects. In design-oriented activities, comparing evidence, logical generalization, critical approach, transforming conclusions into theory, order, planning, effort, using all your strength, not wasting time, comprehensively solving a didactic problem, developing systematic thinking, and increasing a person's cognitive activity are important factors.

According to the subject and content of the project: the project that includes one subject area and the systematic design of interdisciplinary activities are divided into research-related projects. Regardless of the form and type of the project, it is important that they are focused on specific didactic goals and take into account the level of the audience. Projecting requires mutual cooperation and responsibility from the participants of education.

The process of training future primary school teachers to design educational content requires the use of an interdisciplinary, systematic approach, since the lack of creativity in any pedagogical situation creates gaps in creative and professional activity. Therefore, it is advisable to fully organize the training of future primary school teachers in educational institutions and design educational content based on the use of various tools and methods.

The work on designing the content of education consists of two parts: designing the lesson and its implementation. In the process of developing design skills in the educational process of students of the primary education direction, it allows them to identify problems, correctly set goals, plan, and implement them. At the stage of identifying the problem, students have difficulties in analyzing the contradictions and problems in each subject during the teaching of specialized

subjects, and these difficulties are associated with insufficiently developed mental operations of analysis, comparison, and synthesis. This is to some extent due to the fact that today's youth are accustomed to quickly searching for information and finding ready-made answers. This is done on the basis of establishing close cooperation between the teacher and the student in the process of designing a solution to the problem, describing and analyzing the problem situation, and performing tasks on editing the problem.

METHODS

In order to properly organize the process of designing educational content, some topics from specialized subjects are developed on the basis of design and implemented using methods appropriate to the topics. In particular, the design lesson on the subject of mathematics teaching methods for students of primary education is aimed at the rapid, critical and logical thinking of students, and helps future teachers to activate their oral calculations and knowledge. The following methods can be used in this regard: the “Magic table” method, the “Separating numbers from numbers” method, the “Even and odd” method, the “Step by step” method, the “Discussion” method, the “Numbers and puzzles” method. For students of primary education, the subject of teaching methods of the native language. The design lesson is aimed at students' adherence to spelling rules, correct approach to content, and creative thinking. The recommended methods for preparing future teachers to activate their knowledge are the “Conversation” method, the “Sunflower” method, the “correct and beautiful writing” method, the “+ and -” method, the “Assessment” method, the “Continue the wrong letter” method, the “TTT” (Find the correct image) method. In addition, in the design lesson about teaching methods of natural sciences, students of primary education will have the opportunity to deepen their knowledge of this subject and connect it with everyday life. The following methods can be used in this subject: the “Conscious Choice” method, the “Let's Complete Together” method, the “Summarize Ideas” method, the “SMART” method, the “Mind Map”, the “BBB” (I Knew, I Want to Know, I Found Out) method, and the “Best Idea” method are recommended. Lessons organized on the basis of this design not only give a positive effect, but also teach students to use every minute wisely in organizing a lesson and organize a lesson based on a plan. This improves the quality of the lesson and increases student activity. It helps future teachers learn new methods that they can use in the lesson process, and when they start their teaching career, they will realize how interesting, effective, and useful lessons can be if they organize education based on design.

One of the main tasks of primary education is to provide children with knowledge, form their worldview, and prepare them for social life. In order to educate primary school students in a way that meets these requirements, primary school textbooks must also meet these requirements, of course. We will not be mistaken if we say that the new primary school textbooks introduced in schools from 2023-2024 meet these requirements. These textbooks were created by international experts and Uzbek scientists, instilling Uzbek nationalism in a way that meets international assessment systems.

The information provided in the new textbooks encourages students to think creatively, broaden their horizons, and not just memorize what they have read, but to think, analyze, and think logically about what they have read. Let's look at this on the example of a 3rd-4th grade native language textbook. If we look at the 3rd grade native language textbook, in parts II, III, IV, after several topics, the topic “Creativity Hour. Project Work” is given. In part II of the textbook, topics 6, 10, 19, 24 are “Creativity Hour. Project Work”, in part III, topics 6, 10, 23, 29 are “Creativity Hour. Project Work”, in part IV, topics 5, 13, 20, 25 are divided into “Creativity Hour. Project

Work". In the 4th grade native language textbook, in Part II, topics 6, 11, 20, 26 are divided into "Creativity Hour. Project Work", in Part III, topics 5, 11, 21, 28, 33 are divided into "Creativity Hour. Project Work", and in Part IV, topics 5, 10, 18, 25 are divided into "Creativity Hour. Project Work". We can see that in these textbooks, after the student has been taught several topics, exercises are presented to be completed through a project called "creative hour" to consolidate their knowledge of these topics. For example, a 4th grade textbook is given a text called "Letter to a Friend," and after this text, students are given the task of writing a letter to their friends on this topic. Through this exercise, students learn to create another based on one project, follow the norms of the literary language during the creation of the text, and create a written text in an understandable way. In addition, students are introduced to the types of formal letters in the topics of project work. The topics in these textbooks encourage students to be creative, for example, exercises such as writing a poem or continuing a fairy tale.

By designing the content of education, the teacher uses the lesson time effectively and works with students individually, taking into account their individual psychological characteristics. This opens up a wider path for their deeper mastery of professional subjects. When organizing design work, the application of the didactic task and the problems of solving it are considered. Design is one of the important conditions for organizing the pedagogical process and ensuring its successful course. When designing the pedagogical process, such tasks as:

- a) analyzing the content of pedagogical activity;
- b) predicting the results;
- d) creating a project for implementing the planned activity are performed.

At this stage, the teacher's independent, but at the same time collaboratively with the student, designed activity based on determining the content and means of the educational process takes a leading place.[5, 23]

When planning a lesson, the teacher, of course, wonders about the method by which it will be conducted. On the surface, it seems that each topic can be taught using any method, but in practice this is not possible. A number of objective and subjective reasons and existing conditions negatively affect this. Monitoring student activity plays an important role in the design of the educational process. Therefore, designing the monitoring process also requires a particularly qualified approach from the teacher. Especially in primary grades, the teacher should pay special attention to this stage. In primary grades, the subjects in which projecting is most often used are native language and reading, natural sciences, and technology. In these lessons, it is important for the teacher to correctly design the project so that the topics are presented to students in a consistent, clear, and understandable way. Through properly organized lessons, students develop skills such as a clear idea of the topic, connecting the topic with life, and finding terms appropriate to the topic.

In the process of designing educational content, the teacher can use project-based learning. Project-based learning is a student-centered approach in which learning is organized through projects based on real-world tasks or problems. Educational content plays a crucial role in modern education and contributes to effective learning, accessibility, and adaptability. Educational content makes it easier for students to acquire and understand new knowledge and skills, allows people to learn at their own pace, considering different learning styles and preferences, and educational resources include multimedia elements, quizzes, and interactive features, which makes learning more interesting.

Educational design is a phenomenon that arises as a result of the interaction of new trends and the development of pedagogical theory and innovative practice. In foreign countries, including Russia, online paid courses called “Pedagogical Design of Educational Content” have been organized. This course is intended for students interested in pedagogy and who want to develop skills in developing educational content. The purpose of the program is to train students in the process of creating and organizing educational material and content based on modern pedagogical approaches. Students learn to analyze the needs of students, determine the goals and objectives of the educational process, plan and develop its content, effectively use information technologies, and adapt programs for different age groups and characteristics of students.

Project-based lessons require the teacher to be able to design a lesson in a well-thought-out, high-quality, work-oriented manner in a way that attracts students to the process. When organizing the educational process on a project basis, the teacher is required to play the role of a comprehensive creative educator, not an active operator. The problem of designing educational content in primary grades is important and relevant for both theory and practice. Project-based education allows solving the following urgent educational problems and meets the requirements of the time:

- ensures the implementation of education in a situation that is highly approximated to real life;
- allows the evaluation of theoretical information with practical activities and the involvement of students in the process of active independent knowledge;
- ensures the formation and development of professional and basic skills.

The process of teaching primary school teachers to design educational content begins when they are studying at the bachelor's level. To do this, the task of the teacher in higher education institutions is to create conditions for the effective independent creative activities of students and give them tasks to prepare projects. During the presentation of the projects created by the students, the teacher should tell them about the advantages and disadvantages of the projects they created. Through this method, they learn to create a project, develop projects to participate in various competitions. They learn to develop a technological map of how to organize theoretical and practical classes, that is, to develop a detailed plan for how to conduct a lesson, and in general, to plan their activities.

A primary school student perceives the world around him as a whole. For him, it is not the names of natural science, Russian, English, music and other subjects that are interesting, but the variety of sounds, colors, and sizes of objects in the world around him. The teacher feels and knows that children need to be taught to see the connection between nature and everything in everyday life. Therefore, if, by designing the content of education, the teacher explains the subjects to the students in an interesting way, connecting them with life, and has the student complete this project, the student's project completed during this lesson will be both interesting and effective. For example, in a mathematics lesson, the following small project can be used to teach shapes: shapes such as a circle, a rectangle, a square, a triangle, a cone are given, students first draw objects corresponding to these shapes, giving examples from everyday life, and then use these shapes to make something. They can build a house using triangles, rectangles, and squares. This project encourages students to think, imagine, and think logically. Especially in elementary grades, using such small projects is very convenient, easy, and interesting. In addition, today's demand is to teach students to work independently and think logically. Based on such small projects, the entire

lesson and educational process are gradually covered. Teachers who start organizing lessons in this way later plan their entire activities and thus design the educational content.

CONCLUSION

Primary education is the main foundation of education, and the knowledge given to students at this stage constitutes their main information reserve, and therefore the responsibility of the primary school teacher is great. If future primary school teachers are taught to design educational content, the teacher's work will be easier and more effective. Designing requires the teacher to have high knowledge, potential, skills, and a strong understanding of modern information technology. Therefore, in order to design each lesson, the teacher must not only know the necessary knowledge on that subject, but also know how to convey that knowledge to students on the basis of design. That is, first of all, the teacher must be creative and be able to use innovations effectively. He must be able to design each lesson and convey it to the student in an interesting way.

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